

Bleeding complications associated with ultrasound-guided upper extremity peripheral nerve blocks and associated risk factors

A protocol for a retrospective observational cohort study.

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Introduction

Peripheral nerve blocks (PNBs) are generally considered safe, and procedural ultrasound guidance is increasingly used, enhancing accuracy and success rates [1–5]. Their use is widely implemented in the perioperative setting and is expanding beyond the operating theatre, e.g. to emergency departments, thereby broadening the patient population [6–8]. Concurrently, population ageing, increasing multimorbidity, and the wider use of more easily administered direct oral anticoagulants have contributed to a growing number of patients receiving antithrombotic therapy [9,10]. Consequently, the need to perform PNBs in patients receiving antithrombotic therapy, who may be at increased risk of bleeding, is expanding. Although bleeding complications after PNBs are rare, with an overall estimated occurrence of approximately 0.82% (ranging from 0.64% to 1.0%), robust evidence regarding their safety profile remains limited [11].

Given the close anatomical proximity of peripheral nerves to vascular structures, PNBs carry a theoretical risk of vascular puncture and subsequent bleeding. PNBs are commonly categorised as superficial or deep, with deep nerve blocks located near non-compressible structures, where ultrasound visualisation may be more challenging [12–15]. Current guidelines classify deep nerve blocks as high-risk blocks to be managed with temporary suspension of relevant antithrombotic therapy before the PNB procedure, in accordance with recommendations for neuraxial blockades [12–15]. In the upper extremity, infraclavicular brachial plexus blocks are the only block considered deep, despite other practice advisories considering it a block of “intermediate risk” of bleeding complications comparable to interscalene and supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks [16]. In the literature, vascular puncture during PNB procedure is inconsistently equated with a bleeding complication [16,17]. Although ultrasound guidance is associated with a reduced risk of vascular puncture, its use does not alter recommendations regarding antithrombotic management [2,12]. Current evidence on bleeding complications after infraclavicular nerve block is limited to a few case reports and a cohort study reporting a 3% incidence of ecchymosis or haematomas, without association to active antithrombotic therapy reported [1,14,16,18,19]. Thus, categorising the infraclavicular block as a high-risk block is primarily based on anatomical considerations and expert consensus, highlighting the need for larger cohort studies. Accordingly, the aim with this retrospective observational cohort study is to estimate the incidence of clinically relevant bleeding complications following upper-extremity PNBs. Secondly, to identify potential associated risk factors, including nerve block type, antithrombotic therapy and biochemical coagulopathy. We hypothesise that clinically relevant bleeding complications following ultrasound-guided upper-extremity peripheral

nerve blocks are rare, and not associated with antithrombotic therapy, block type, or biochemical coagulopathy.

Methods

A retrospective observational cohort study using prospectively collected clinical data from patients undergoing upper extremity surgery who received ultrasound-guided PNB perioperatively. The manuscript will be developed and reported in accordance with the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) principles [20].

Setting and Population

The cohort will include all adult patients (≥ 18 years) who received an ultrasound-guided upper extremity PNB perioperatively in public hospitals in the Capital and Zealand Regions of Denmark, between 1 January 2017, and 14 November 2025, covering approximately 2.8 million inhabitants [21]. Patients will be identified through their unique Danish personal identification number (CPR number) linked to the specific surgical and anaesthetic procedure using the NOMESCO Classification of Surgical Procedures [22].

Inclusion criteria:

- Adult patients (≥ 18 years)
- Upper extremity ultrasound-guided PNB (single-shot or catheter), during a surgical hospital admission (elective or acute).

No exclusion criteria will be applied.

Outcomes and Exposures

- **Primary outcome:** PNB-related clinically relevant bleeding complications within seven days.

PNB-related clinically relevant bleeding is defined as bleeding requiring medical or invasive intervention; bleeding requiring blood transfusion; fatal bleeding resulting in death and/or bleeding resulting in haematoma formation with symptomatic injury to nerves or other adjacent tissues.

Events will be identified using the predefined screening criteria listed below, and all positive events screened will be confirmed by manual review of the patient's medical records to ensure PNB relation and bleeding relevance (see **Figure 2**):

- Free text mining of patient health records to identify text mentioning of a clinical bleeding in relation to a PNB-related term (see detailed description in the *Data Collection* section and **Appendix 1**);
- Documented blood aspiration during PNB procedure;
- Vascular surgical or radiological intervention in the shoulder, neck, or upper extremity region within seven days of the PNB procedure;
- Haemothorax and/or pleura drain due to a haemothorax within seven days of the PNB procedure;
- CT angiography or vascular ultrasound of the upper extremity within seven days of the PNB procedure;

Secondary outcomes

- 30-day readmission post-PNB procedure (Y/N).
- Post-PNB procedure in-hospital length of stay (hours)

Exposures

Primary exposure

- Active antithrombotic therapy at the time of the PNB procedure.

Defined as active treatment with one or more of the following agents without relevant pre-procedural suspension recommended from the Peripheral Regional Anaesthesia and Bleeding Risk report by the Danish Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis [13] (Y/N), (see detailed description in **Appendix 2**):

- Vitamin K antagonists (VKA) (warfarin, phenprocoumon)
- Indirect factor Xa inhibitors (fondaparinux) ≥ 2.5 mg daily
- Direct oral anticoagulants (DOAC) (rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, dabigatran)
- Low molecular weight heparins (LMWH) >3.500 IE (enoxaparin, tinzaparin, dalteparin)
- P2Y12 inhibitors (clopidogrel, prasugrel, ticagrelor)

Secondary exposures

- Pre-existing biochemical coagulopathy at the time of PNB procedure, defined as the presence of one or more of the following in the latest blood test and within 90 days before the PNB procedure (Y/N)
 - INR >1.5 [13]
 - Thrombocytes in plasma $<20 \times 10^9/L$ [13]

- PNB type (categorical)
 - Deep block: Infraclavicular brachial plexus block.
 - Superficial block: Axillary, interscalene, supraclavicular, suprascapular, single nerve blocks (radial, ulnar, median or musculocutaneous or a combination hereof)

Covariates:

- Injection technique (single-shot or nerve catheter).
- Type of surgical procedure performed (categorical)
- Intraoperative blood loss (mL)
- Time between PNB procedure and surgery (hours)

Baseline data and study characteristics

- Age (years)
- Sex (male/female)
- Body mass index (BMI, kg/m²)
- American Society of Anesthesiology (ASA) classification (I-IV)
- Admission type (acute or elective)
- Hospital site
- Indication for PNB (primary anaesthesia or postoperative pain relief)
- Blood aspiration during PNB procedure (Y/N).
- Latest relevant blood test results: haemoglobin, creatinine, thrombocytes, international normalised ratio (INR).
- Comorbidity: Liver disease, chronic or acute kidney disease, diabetes, ischemic heart disease, atrial fibrillation or atrial flutter, arterial sclerosis, congenital coagulopathy (Y/N).
- All-cause mortality within seven days of the PNB procedure (days)
- Transfusion of red blood cells units within 48 hours after PNB administration [23]
- Decrease of haemoglobin >1.24 mmol/L (>2 g/dL) within 48 hours after PNB procedure [23]

A detailed list of variables is provided in **Appendix 3**.

Data collection

Data will be extracted from the Electronic Health Record system *Sundhedsplatformen* (Epic Systems Corporation, WI, USA), via the AI and Automation in Anaesthesia (TRIPLE-A) database (www.triplea.dk). The database contains granular data from approximately 1.4 million anaesthetic procedures, including around 160,000 PNBs [24]. Patients are registered in the database through hospital admissions, containing one or more surgical contact serial numbers (CSN-IDs) linked to an anaesthesia CSN-ID. Data are collected prospectively for routine clinical care and subsequently integrated into the TRIPLE-A database for epidemiological, quality improvement, and research purposes. Study variables derived from the database have been rigorously coded by multiple data-branches and validated in clinician-reviewed test sets, including both random and targeted samples, to ensure data quality [24]. Free-text mining is an approach for identifying and extracting clinically relevant information from unstructured narrative text, such as medical record notes, using predefined search terms, pattern recognition, and contextual rules. In this study, it will be applied to detect potential bleeding complications that may not be captured reliably by structured registry variables alone. Free-text mining will be conducted in R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria) using rule-based regular expression matching with the *stringr* package, supported by a data table for data handling and aggregation. The algorithm identifies predefined term patterns, assesses their position and proximity within the clinical notes, and applies text-window-based rules (**Appendix 1**). Two independent authors will screen all notes identified by free-text mining. All potential events of the primary outcome will undergo full medical record review by the same authors to confirm clinical relevance and relation to the PNB procedure. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion; if residual disagreements remain, a third senior author will be involved.

Approval for the initial database extraction was obtained from 'Team for journaldata, videnskabsetik og forskningsstøtte, Region Hovedstaden' (Approval number R-23038250; 14 July 2023). Furthermore, approval has also been granted for the transfer of medical record data from the database to this research project (Approval number R-25070971; 23 October 2025).

Defining the primary outcome variable

The primary outcome, PNB-related clinically relevant bleeding complications, was initially defined only using structured data due to the size of the cohort. The initial definition included red blood cell transfusion within 48 hours after PNB administration, a decrease in haemoglobin >1.24 mmol/L (>2 g/dL) within seven days after the PNB procedure, and/or vascular surgical or radiological intervention in the shoulder/neck region. This definition was inspired by the bleeding criteria proposed by

Schulman et al[23]. After five rounds of targeted validation in the lower-extremity PNB cohort using 20 random sample checks in each round, followed by code adaptation, no PNB-related bleeding events were identified. The structured-data definition was considered to have limited sensitivity and to capture surgical rather than PNB-related bleeding predominantly. Consequently, to improve sensitivity, the primary outcome was redefined to incorporate unstructured narrative data through structured free-text mining, drawing on well-known and recognised methods used in systematic reviews. To retain clinical relevance, structured data reflecting potential identification of treatment of PNB-related bleeding are still included. All potential bleeding events identified by this method will undergo a full medical record review to ensure high specificity.

Data handling

Data will be anonymised before analysis and stored in a secure database with restricted access to ensure patient confidentiality and compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation[25]. Prior to analysis, the dataset will undergo pre-processing and validation procedures, including checks for missing values, duplicate records, data inconsistencies, and systematic errors, e.g coding errors. Only validated data will be included in the analyses to ensure accuracy and reliability. The anonymised dataset will be retained for a specified period and deleted thereafter.

Patients may contribute more than one PNB observation if they received multiple upper extremity PNBs during the same procedure, within the same hospital admission, or across separate admissions. As clinically relevant bleeding complications are expected to be rare, each individual PNB will be considered a separate event at risk. Potential within-patient clustering will be accounted for in the statistical analyses.

Statistical analysis

Baseline characteristics will be summarised using descriptive statistics. Continuous variables will be presented as means with standard deviations (SDs) or medians with interquartile ranges (IQRs), depending on the distribution. Distributional assumptions will be assessed by visual inspection of histograms and quantile–quantile plots. Categorical variables will be presented as counts and percentages.

The primary outcome will be analysed using multivariable mixed-effects logistic regression with a patient-level random intercept to account for within-patient clustering. Based on clinical relevance and potential confounding, all models will be adjusted for the predefined listed covariates, age, sex,

BMI, ASA, hospital site, and admission type. If the number of primary outcome events is insufficient to ensure at least 10 events per estimated model parameter (< 100 events), the primary outcome will nevertheless be analysed using the prespecified full model, given that the model assumptions are met. The results will, however, be interpreted with caution due to potential model instability and imprecision. Furthermore, each component of the primary outcome definition will be analysed separately as an explorative analysis. For patients who die within seven days of the PNB procedure, the observation period will be limited to the period from the PNB procedure to death. Effect estimates will be reported as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). If the number of primary outcome events does not exceed 100, the primary outcome will furthermore be presented descriptively, including a case-by-case summary of all confirmed events.

For secondary outcomes, analyses will be restricted to the prespecified secondary exposure, PNB type, to assess whether deep or superficial PNBs are associated with 30-day readmission and post-PNB-procedure length of hospital stay. Associations between antithrombotic therapy or biochemical coagulopathy and the secondary outcomes will not be interpreted as exposure–outcome effects, given the likely confounding by multimorbidity and baseline illness severity. The secondary binary outcome, 30-day readmission, will be analysed using multivariable mixed-effects logistic regression with a patient-level random intercept. If the model does not converge, the hospital site will instead be included as a random effect. Post-procedure length of stay will be analysed using linear mixed-effects regression with a patient-level random intercept. If the length of stay is right-skewed, the outcome will be log-transformed before analysis or non-parametric tests used as relevant, and results will be back-transformed and presented as geometric mean ratios with 95% CIs. Secondary outcomes will, in addition to the defined adjustment parameters used for the primary outcome model, be adjusted by the latest preprocedural laboratory results and comorbidity. Variables occurring after the PNB procedure, including blood transfusion and postoperative haemoglobin decrease, will not be included as adjustment variables. Categorical group comparisons in descriptive analyses will be performed using Fisher's exact test when appropriate.

Unadjusted regression analyses will be performed for the predefined exposure–outcome associations for descriptive purposes and to provide both unadjusted and adjusted estimates, in line with STROBE reporting recommendations[20]. The conclusion will be based solely on the adjusted analysis.

Analyses involving specific PNB types with fewer than 100 outcome observations will be included separately, but interpretation will be cautious due to limited precision.

Subgroup analyses of the primary outcome will be performed to assess whether PNB-related clinically relevant bleeding complications and potential associated risk factors vary across clinically relevant

subgroups. The following subgroup analyses are planned a priori: deep vs superficial PNB, anticoagulant vs antiplatelet treatment, and BMI >35 kg/m².

Sensitivity analyses will assess the robustness of the primary outcome to alternative model specifications and adjustment sets. These will be restricted to patients with sufficient pre-procedural in-hospital admission time to only account for the documentation of interruption of antithrombotic therapy in the medical records, minimising the uncertainty of proper interruption of antithrombotic therapy, potentially influenced by patient compliance and the free-text search incorporated in this exposure variable.

All statistical tests will be two-sided, and p-values below 0.05 will be considered statistically significant. Analyses of additional exposures, secondary outcomes, subgroup analyses, and sensitivity analyses will not be adjusted for multiplicity and will therefore be interpreted as exploratory.

Missing data will be quantified and reported for all variables. Under the assumption that data are missing at random, multiple imputation by chained equations will be applied to covariates and exposure variables with substantial missingness (>10 %). The imputation model will include all variables used in the analysis models, including the outcome variable as a predictor. However, outcome values will not be imputed for the primary analysis, and when an analysis undergoes multiple imputations, a complete-case analysis will be conducted as a sensitivity analysis.

Statistical analyses will be performed using the latest available stable version of R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

Results (tentative presentation)

Table 1 – Baseline and study characteristics

Variable	All n = [X]	Antithrombotic therapy n = [X]	No or timely paused antithrombotic therapy n = [X]	Missing	P- value
DEMOGRAPHICS					
Age, median (IQR), years	[XX] ([XX–XX])	[XX] ([XX–XX])	[XX] ([XX–XX])	[X] ([X]%)	—
Male sex, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
BMI, median (IQR), kg/m ²	[XX] ([XX–XX])	[XX] ([XX–XX])	[XX] ([XX–XX])	[X] ([X]%)	—
ASA classification, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
All-cause mortality 7D, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
I	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
II	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
III	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
IV	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
PROCEDURE CHARACTERISTICS					
Acute hospital admission, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Indication for PNB - surgical anaesthesia, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Injection technique - single shot, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Blood aspiration during PNB, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Time from PNB procedure to surgery, mean (SD), hours	[XX] ([X])	[XX] ([X])	[XX] ([X])	[X] ([X]%)	—
Intraoperative blood loss, mean (SD), mL	[XX] ([X])	[XX] ([X])	[XX] ([X])	[X] ([X]%)	—
Transfusion of RBC* <48H, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
NERVE BLOCK TYPE, n (%)					
Infraclavicular (deep block)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Axillary (superficial)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Interscalene (superficial)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Supraclavicular (superficial)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Single nerve blocks**	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
ANTITHROMBOTIC THERAPY, n (%)					
Vitamin K antagonist (VKA)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Fondaparinux (Arixtra)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Direct oral anticoagulant	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Low molecular weight heparin	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
P2Y12 inhibitor	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
COMORBIDITIES, n (%)					
Atrial fibrillation or flutter	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Ischaemic heart disease	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Arterial sclerosis	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Kidney disease (acute or chronic)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Liver disease	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Diabetes mellitus	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Congenital bleeding disorders	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
BLOOD TESTS					
Thrombocytes, median (IQR), ×10 ⁹ /L	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X] ([X]%)	—
INR, median (IQR)	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X] ([X]%)	—
Creatinine, median (IQR), μmol/L	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X] ([X]%)	—
Haemoglobin, median (IQR), mmol/L	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X–X.X])	[X] ([X]%)	—
Haemoglobin decrease >1.24 after PNB procedure, n (%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
BIOCHEMICAL COAGULOPATHY, n(%)					
Pre-existing biochemical coagulopathy	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
INR > 1.5	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—
Thrombocytes < 20 × 10 ⁹ /L	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	—

*Red blood cells, **radial, ulnar, median or musculocutaneous or a combination thereof

Consort diagram

Primary Outcome

Clinically relevant bleeding related to the PNB procedure

	Unadjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	P
Primary exposure			
Antithrombotic therapy	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	X.XXX
Secondary exposures			
Biochemical coagulopathy	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	X.XXX
Deep block	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	X.XXX

Adjusted for: injection technique, surgery type, time between PNB procedure and surgery, intraoperative blood loss, age, sex, BMI, ASA, hospital site, admission type

Clinically relevant bleeding related to the PNB procedure

Nerve block type	Procedures, n	Bleedings, n (%)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)
Axillary	[X]	[X] ([X]%)	Reference
Infraclavicular	[X]	[X] ([X]%)	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])
Interscalene	[X]	[X] ([X]%)	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])
Supraclavicular	[X]	[X] ([X]%)	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])
Single nerve blocks*	[X]	[X] ([X]%)	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])

*radial, ulnar, median or musculocutaneous or a combination thereof

Adjusted for: injection technique, surgery type, time between PNB procedure and surgery, intraoperative blood loss, age, sex, BMI, ASA, hospital site, admission type

If < 100 events:

Case-by-case description of bleeding events related to the PNB procedure

Case nr.	PNB type	Patient description	Antithrombotic therapy	PNB procedure description	Consequences of bleeding
1					
2					
3					
4					
...					

Secondary outcomes

	All	Missing	Unadjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	P
Readmission < 30 days, n (%)					
Deep block	[X] ([X]%)	[X] ([X]%)	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	X.XXX
Post procedure length of stay, median (IQR), hours					
Deep block	[X] ([X-X])	[X] ([X]%)	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	[X.X] ([X.X-X.X])	X.XXX

Adjusted for: injection technique, surgery type, time between PNB procedure and surgery, intraoperative blood loss, age, sex, BMI, ASA, hospital site, admission type, comorbidities, latest pre-procedure blood samples.

Discussion

This observational cohort study will, to our knowledge, be the largest study assessing potential bleeding complications associated with upper-extremity PNBs. Given the presumed rare occurrence of bleeding complications after PNBs, large-scale cohort studies are required to identify sufficient number of events to provide more precise estimates of the incidence and associated risk factors [11]. Thus, this study has the potential to inform future updates of guidelines and support clinical decision-making in patients receiving antithrombotic therapy.

The clinical relevance of this question is substantial. Antithrombotic therapy is prescribed to prevent and reduce the risk of thromboembolic complications. Therefore, temporary interruption may increase the risk of thromboembolic events, potentially resulting in ischaemia and organ damage. When interruption of antithrombotic therapy is unfavourable, e.g. due to the risk of thromboembolic events, or not possible, alternative anaesthetic strategies, such as general anaesthesia, must be considered. General anaesthesia, however, is associated with other potential risks, such as haemodynamic and respiratory complications [26,27]. Furthermore, avoidance of regional anaesthesia may necessitate alternative analgesic methods, potentially increasing peri- and postoperative opioid consumption with the inherent risk of opioid-related adverse drug events, increased patient discomfort and impaired mobilisation[28,29].

Strengths and limitations

Given the expected low incidence of bleeding complications associated with PNBs, a large study population is essential to achieve adequate statistical power to detect even slight differences in risk. A prospective cohort study or randomised controlled trial is inappropriate and impossible to perform, both ethically and due to the required sample size. By using pre-existing data, this study enables the inclusion of a large, unselected cohort, thereby enhancing the representativeness of the study population and reducing the risk of systematic bias. This design is both time- and cost-efficient, enabling the analysis of multiple outcomes across a broad, clinically relevant sample.

Several limitations of this study should, however, be acknowledged. The key limitation is the challenge of reliably distinguishing surgery-related bleeding from bleeding attributable to the PNB procedure. This is mitigated by including free-text mining, followed by screening notes and reviewing full patient records for potential events. However, free-text mining is based on presumptions and presumed causalities, which creates a risk of underreporting.

Additionally, estimates of temporary suspension of antithrombotic therapy may be subject to misclassification due to incomplete documentation and considerable inter-patient variability. This

observational study is based on pre-existing clinical data, which may be incomplete for specific patient groups. Despite adjustments for predefined covariates, the design remains inherently vulnerable to residual confounding. Confounding by indication may also be present, as patients with more severe underlying conditions and multimorbidity are more likely to receive antithrombotic therapy and may have a higher baseline risk of bleeding complications, 30-day readmission and post-procedure length of stay independently of the PNB itself. Clinicians may refrain from performing deep peripheral nerve blocks in patients receiving antithrombotic therapy, in accordance with current guidelines, thereby introducing selection bias. Furthermore, PNB type may correlate with different surgical procedures, each with distinct risk profiles and postoperative regimens that may independently impact 30-day readmission and post-procedure length of stay. In addition, the accuracy of the data used depends on the quality of routine clinical documentation, which may be inconsistent or incomplete, potentially leading to information bias or misclassification of exposures, outcomes, or patient eligibility. Finally, causal relationships cannot be established from observational associations, and unmeasured factors may still influence the results despite statistical adjustment and sensitivity analyses.

Declaration of the use of generative artificial intelligence-assisted technology

ChatGPT (OpenAI) and Claude Sonnet 4.6 were used to improve language and support code development for the free-text mining strategy (**Appendix 1**). All outputs were subsequently meticulously reviewed, verified and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final version of the protocol.

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Appendix

Appendix 1 – Free-text search in clinical notes.

Parameter	Value	Rationale
Note retrieval time window	-2 hours to + 7 days from peripheral block procedure.	This approach ensures that clinical notes recorded in close temporal proximity to the peripheral nerve block are retrieved.
Maximum distance between 'bleeding' and 'block' terms for a positive match	50 words	A bleeding term and a block term must co-occur within 50 words to trigger a positive match. A comprehensive list of the bleeding and block terms is provided in relevant tables below.
Look-back window	80 characters	A positive bleeding match was considered invalid if a negation term occurred within the preceding 80 characters*
Look-ahead window	80 characters	A positive bleeding match was considered invalid if a negation term occurred within the following 80 characters*
Look-back window (block exclusions)	60 characters	The code searches 60 characters preceding each block match for exclusion terms. A comprehensive list of relevant excluded block terms is provided below.
Context window (irrelevant context check)	100 characters	The code checks 100 characters on either side of a candidate match for irrelevant clinical context*.
Fuzzy matching distance	≤ 1 character	Bleeding terms with fuzzy matching used a word-by-word Levenshtein distance algorithm (distance ≤ 1), allowing up to one character insertion, deletion, or substitution per word, accommodating minor spelling variants and typographical errors in clinical notes. Strict bleeding terms are matched by exact regular expression only.

* Exclusion and Negations filters, including irrelevant context, are explained comprehensively in a separate table below

Note types included in the search ('Danish' term in Sundhedsplatformen).	Description
Continuation note ('Kontinuationsnotat')	All ongoing inpatient clinical progress notes in the patient journal, independent of the referred speciality or occupation.
Status note ('statusnotat')	Clinical status summary
Admission note ('AOP', 'AOP (skrivebeskyttet)', 'AOP (tillægsnotat')	Admission notes including the write-protected versions, and any addendum to the admission notes.
Consultation note ('Tilsynsnotat')	Note recorded during specialist consultation
Surgery description notes ('Operationsbeskrivelse') with vascular surgery origin.	Notes describing the vascular surgical procedure.
PNB procedure note ('Procedurenotat')	Note describing the PNB procedure.

Bleeding terms		
<p>bleeding_terms_strict <- paste0("(",paste(c ("\\bbl(?:ø oe o)dning(?!s?vagt)[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "\\bbl(?:ø oe o)der\\b", "\\bbl(?:ø oe o)dte\\b", "\\bbl(?:ø oe o)dt\\b", "\\bfterbl(?:ø oe o)d[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "(?!portion[[:space:]-])bblood\\b", "\\bbloodansmiling[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "\\bansmiling[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "\\bh(?:æ æ e a)?matom[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "\\b(?:sgillatio suggillation)[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "\\b(?:ekkyamos ecchymos ekchymos)[[:alpha:]]*\\b", "\\bekstravasation[[:alpha:]]*\\b"),collapse = " ")</p> <p>bleeding_terms_fuzzy <- c("blødning", "blødningen", "blødninger", "blødningskomplikation", "blødning", "blødningen", "blodninger", "bloedning", "bloedningen", "bloedninger", "efterblød", "efterblødning", "efterblødninger", "efterblod", "efterblødning", "efterblodninger", "efterbloed", "efterbloedning", "efterbloedninger", "blodansamling", "blodansamlingen", "blodansamlinger", "ansamling", "ansamlingen", "ansamlinger", "hæmatom", "hæmatomet", "hæmatomer", "hematom", "hematomet", "hematomer", "haematom", "haematomet", "haematomer", "hmatom", "hmatomet", "hmatomer", "sugillation", "sugillationen", "sugillationer", "suggillation", "suggillationen", "suggillationer", "ekkyamos", "ekkyosen", "ekkyoser", "ecchymos", "ecchymosen", "ecchymoser", "ekchymos", "ekchymosen", "ekchymoser", "ekstravasation", "ekstravasationen", "ekstravasationer"</p>		
Regex component	Matched words (Danish)	Explanation
bleeding_terms_strict – matched by exact regular expression		
\\bbl(?:ø oe o)dning(?!s?vagt)[[:alpha:]]*\\b	blødning, blødningen, blødninger, blødnings, blødningsrisiko, blødningsrisikoen, blødningskomplikation <i>BUT NOT:</i> blødningsvagt, blødningsvagten	All morphological variations of the noun 'bleeding' including 'bleeding risk' and 'bleeding complication'. Word boundaries are enforced on both sides. Negative lookahead prevents matching 'blødningsvagt' (on-call duty term).
\\bbl(?:ø oe o)der\\b, \\bbl(?:ø oe o)dte\\b, \\bbl(?:ø oe o)dt\\b	bløder, bloeder, bloedte, blødte, blødt, bloedt	Present, simple past and short principal tense of the verb 'to bleed' including (rare alternative spelling). Word boundary enforced after the match.
\\bfterbl(?:ø oe o)d[[:alpha:]]*\\b	efterblødning, efterblødninger, efterblødende	Captures all morphological derivatives of 'after bleeding' (postoperative or secondary bleeding).
(?!portion[[:space:]-])bblood\\b	blod <i>BUT NOT:</i> portionblod, portionblod, blodprøver, blodtryk.	Capture the exact noun 'blood' with negative lookbehind preventing matching when 'portion' (or 'portion-') immediately precedes the term, avoiding unrelated compound words. Word boundary enforced after the match excluding unrelated terms such as 'bloodpressure' and 'bloodsamples'.
\\bbloodansmiling[[:alpha:]]*\\b	blodansamling, blodansamlingen, blodansamlinger, blodansamlingerne	All inflected forms of the noun 'blood collection'.
\\bansmiling[[:alpha:]]*\\b	ansamling, ansamlingen, ansamlinger, ansamlingssted	Broad term 'accumulations' – to also capture non-blood-specific accumulations.
\\bh(?:æ æ e a)?matom[[:alpha:]]*\\b	hæmatom, haematom, hematom, hamatom, hæmatomer, hæmatomet, hæmatomerne	Covers all common orthographic variants of haematoma, including the Latin spelling 'haematom' and the simplified form 'hematom'.

\b(?:sgillatio sugillation)[[:alpha:]]*\b	sugillation, sugillationen, sugillationer, sugillation, sugillationen	Covers all common orthographic variants of the term 'sugillation' including alternative spelling with double-g; both variants are captured.
\b(?:ekkyamos ecchymos ekchymos)[[:alpha:]]*\b	ekkyamos, ekkyamose, ekkyamosen, ekkyamose, ecchymos, ecchymose, ecchymosis, ekchymos, ekchymose	Danish and latin/international spelling of ecchymosis including a third orthographic variant.
\bekstravasation[[:alpha:]]*\b	ekstravasation, ekstravasationen, ekstravasationer	Term denoting extravasation of fluid or blood into surrounding tissue
bleeding_terms_fuzzy – matched with up to one character insertion, deletion, or substitution		
<p>"blødning", "blødningen", "blødninger", "blødningskomplikation", "blodning", "blodningen", "blodninger", "bloedning", "bloedningen", "bloedninger", "efterblød", "efterblødning", "efterblødninger", "efterblod", "efterblodning", "efterblodninger", "efterbloed", "efterbloedning", "efterbloedninger", "blodansamling", "blodansamlingen", "blodansamlinger", "ansamling", "ansamlingen", "ansamlinger", "hæmatom", "hæmatomet", "hæmatomer", "hematom", "hematomet", "hematometer", "haematom", "haematomet", "haematomer", "hmatom", "hmatomet", "hmatometer", "sugillation", "sugillationen", "sugillationer", "sugillation", "sugillationen", "sugillationer", "ekkyamos", "ekkyamosen", "ekkyamoser", "ecchymos", "ecchymosen", "ecchymoser", "ekchymos", "ekchymosen", "ekchymoser", "ekstravasation", "ekstravasationen", "ekstravasationer"</p>		<p>All bleeding terms explicitly listed in this predefined search dictionary are subject to the fuzzy matching. The fuzzy matching algorithm compares individual words in the free-text notes with the listed bleeding terms and allows a maximum edit distance of one character, defined as one insertion, deletion, or substitution.</p> <p>Because the algorithm operates on individual words rather than regular expression patterns, wildcard suffixes and regular expression syntax, such as [[:alpha:]], cannot be incorporated into the fuzzy matching procedure.</p>

Block pattern		
Regex component	Matched words (Danish)	Explanation
block_terms <- paste0("(", "nerve[:space:~]*blok[:alpha:~]*", "nerve[:space:~]*blokade[:alpha:~]*", "\b(?:nerve(?:n r)? nervegren(?:en e ene)? nervefiber(?:en)? nervefibre(?:ne)? nervestruktur(?:en ererne)? nervestamme(?:n r rme)? nerverod(?:en)? nervørødder(?:ne)? nerveplexus nervus nervi)\b)", "\b(?:ramus rami radix radices truncus fasciulus fasciculi)\b)", "\bplexus[:space:~]*(?:brachialis lumbalis sacralis)\b)", "nerve[:space:~]*kateter[:alpha:~]*", "perineural[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]-]*kateter[:alpha:~]*", "perifer[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]*nerve[:space:~]*blok[:alpha:~]*", "perifer[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]*nerve[:space:~]-]*blokade[:alpha:~]*", "perifer[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]*blokade[:alpha:~]*", "regional[:space:~]*an[æa]stesi[:alpha:~]*", "regionalan[æa]stesi[:alpha:~]*", "regional[:space:~]*analgesi[:alpha:~]*", "regionalanalgesi[:alpha:~]*", "regional[:space:~]-]*blokade[:alpha:~]*", "regional[:space:~]*blok[:alpha:~]*", "perineural[:alpha:~]*", "\bneural(?:te)?\b)", "blokade[:alpha:~]*", "\bblok\b)", "blok[:space:~]*anl[æa]ggelse[:alpha:~]*", "_lokanl[æa]ggelse[:alpha:~]*", "anl[æa]ggelse[:space:~]*af[:space:~]-]*(?:nerve[:space:~]*)?blok[:alpha:~]*", "anlagt[:space:~]*(?:nerve[:space:~]*)?blok[:alpha:~]*", "lagt[:space:~]*(?:nerve[:space:~]-)*?blok[:alpha:~]*", "\bPNB\b)", "\bLIC\b)", "\bFIC\b)", "\bFNB\b)", "\bPENG\b)", "\bl[:space:~]*PACK\b)", "\bIPACK\b)", "\bTAP\b)", "\bTQL\b)", "\bQLB\b)", "\bPECS\b)", ")")		
Generic nerve block and regional anaesthesia terms		
nerve[:space:~]*blok[:alpha:~]*, nerve[:space:~]*blokade[:alpha:~]*	nerveblok, nerveblokken, nerveblokade, nerve-blok, nerve blok, nerveblokering, nerveblokaden, nerve-blokade, nerve blokade	The noun 'nerve block'. Permits a space or hyphen between 'nerve' and 'block', with the Danish spelling 'blok' or 'blokade'.
\b(?:nerve(?:n r)? nervegren(?:en e ene)? nervefiber(?:en)? nervefibre(?:ne)? nervestruktur(?:en ererne)? nervestamme(?:n r rme)? nerverod(?:en)? nervørødder(?:ne)? nerveplexus nervus nervi)\b)"	nerve, nerven, nerver, nervegren, nervegrenen, nervegrene, nervegrenene, nervefiber, nervefiberen, nervefibre, nervefibrene, nervestruktur, nervestrukturen, nervestrukturerne, nervestamme, nervestammerne, nervestammen, nervestammer, nerverod, nerveroden, nervørødder, nervørødderne, nerveplexus, nervus, nervi	Explicit anatomical terms for nerve structures with enforced word boundaries, ensuring only complete word forms are matched. Excluding irrelevant wording with 'nerve'.
"\b(?:ramus rami radix radices truncus fasciulus fasciculi)\b)"	ramus, rami, radix, radices, truncus, fasciulus, fasciculi	Latin anatomical terms for nerve components.
"\bplexus[:space:~]-]*(?:brachialis lumbalis sacralis)\b)"	plexus brachialis, plexus lumbalis, plexus sacralis	Named nerve plexuses relevant to peripheral nerve block procedures, with optional space or hyphen between 'plexus' and the anatomical qualifier.
nerve[:space:~]*kateter[:alpha:~]*	nervekateter, nervekateteret, nerve-kateter	Any morphology of the noun 'continuous perineural catheter'.
perineural[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]-]*kateter[:alpha:~]*	perineuralt kateter, perineural kateter, perineural-kateter	Explicitly all terms of 'perineural catheters'.
perifer[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]*nerve[:space:~]-]*blok[:alpha:~]*, perifer[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]*nerve[:space:~]-]*blokade[:alpha:~]*	perifer nerveblok, perifere nerveblokke, perifer nerve-blok, perifer nerveblokade, perifere nerveblokader	Full compound expression of 'peripheral nerve block' with the Danish spelling 'blok' or 'blokade'.
perifer[:alpha:~]*[:space:~]-]*blokade[:alpha:~]*	perifer blokade, perifere blokader, perifer-blokade	Full compound expression of the shortened form, omitting 'nerve'.
regional[:space:~]*an[æa]stesi[:alpha:~]*, regionalan[æa]stesi[:alpha:~]*	regionalanæstesi, regional anæstesi, regional anestesi, regional-anæstesi, regionalanæstesi, regionalanestesi	All terms expressing 'regional anaesthesia'. Accommodates both 'æ' and 'a' in 'anæstesi' and compounded forms (no space)

regional[:space:~]*analgesi[:alpha:~]*, regionalanalgesi[:alpha:~]*	regional analgesi, regionalanalgesi, regionalanalgesi	Pain-management-focused formulation 'regional analgesia' including compound form (no space).
regional[:space:~]*blokade[:alpha:~]*, regional[:space:~]*blok[:alpha:~]*	regional blokade, regionalblokade, regional-blokade, regional blok, regionalblok	The term 'regional block' with the Danish spelling 'blok' or 'blokade' and abbreviated forms.
perineural[:alpha:~]*	perineural, perineuralt, perineurale	All inflected forms of 'perineural'.
\\bneural(?:t e)?\\b	neural, neuralt, neurale	Adjectival form of 'neural', captured with strict word boundaries.
blokade[:alpha:~]*, \\blok\\b	Blokade, blokaden, blokader, blokaderne, blok	All inflected forms of the standalone noun 'block' with the Danish spelling 'blok' or 'blokade'. Word boundary enforced after the match 'blok'.
blok[:space:~]*anl[æa]ggelse[:alpha:~]*, blokan[æa]ggelse[:alpha:~]*	blokanæggelse, blok anlæggelse, blok-anlæggelse, blokanlæggelse, blokanlæggelse	All terms of the procedural placement noun 'block placement' including the compound forms
anl[æa]ggelse[:space:~]*af[:space:~]*(?::nerve[:space:~]*)?blok[:alpha:~]*	anlæggelse af blok, anlæggelse af nerveblok, anlæggelse af nerveblok	Captures procedural phrasing describing the act of placing a block, 'placement of [nerve] block'
anlagt[:space:~]*(?::nerve[:space:~]*)?blok[:alpha:~]*, lagt[:space:~]*(?::nerve[:space:~]*)?blok[:alpha:~]*	anlagt blok, anlagt nerveblok, anlagt nerve blok, lagt blok, lagt nerveblok, lagt nerve-blok	Past participle constructions describing a completed block placement: 'block placed/sited' including a shorter participial variant
\\bPNB\\b	PNB	Abbreviation for Peripheral Nerve Block. Strict word boundaries enforced.
Specific block abbreviations		
\\bLIC\\b	LIC	Lateral infraclavicular block.
\\bFIC\\b	FIC	Fascia iliaca compartment block.
\\bFNB\\b	FNB	Femoral nerve block.
\\bPENG\\b	PENG	Pericapsular nerve group block.
\\bI[:space:~]*PACK\\b, \\bIPACK\\b	IPACK, I PACK, I-PACK, IPACK	Infiltration between the popliteal artery and the capsule of the knee. Including compound spelling
\\bTAP\\b	TAP	Transversus abdominis plane block.
\\bTQL\\b	TQL	Transmuscular quadratus lumborum block.
\\bQLB\\b	QLB	Quadratus lumborum block.
\\bPECS\\b	PECS	Pectoral nerve block.

Exclusion terms for block pattern		
The following terms or phrases, when occurring within 60 characters immediately preceding a match in the 'Block pattern', cause that match to be excluded from the search.		
Regex component	Excluded examples	Explanation
<code>\bgren[[:space:]]*</code>	Gren-, gren	Refers to bundle branch (e.g. 'grenblok' = bundle branch block).
<code>\bSA[[:space:]]*</code>	SA	Sinoatrial node; 'SA-blok' denotes a sinoatrial block.
<code>\bAV[[:space:]]*</code>	AV	Atrioventricular node; 'AV-blok' denotes an atrioventricular conduction block.
<code>\brp\.[[:space:]][:punct:]]*</code>	rp., rp	Prescription abbreviation may appear in medication lists immediately before the prescription of a peripheral nerve block in the journal.
<code>\bvelfungerende[[:space:]][:punct:]]*</code>	velfungerende	Describes a block that is working effectively (functioning well) — indicative of an uncomplicated course.
<code>\bgod[[:space:]]+effekt[[:space:]]+af[[:space:]][:punct:]]*</code>	god effekt af	'good effect of' e.g. good effect of the block — indicates an uncomplicated block

Exclusion and Negations filters, including irrelevant context			
Mechanism	Danish text matched	English equivalent	Explanation
Pre-hit negation	Ingen, intet, ikke, ej, uden, kirurgisk, peroperativ, intraoperativt, risiko for, risiko for komplikationer, mulighed for, risici for, komplikationer:, afkræftet/afkræfter/afkræftes, benægtet/benægtes/benægter, ingen tegn til/ingen tegn på, uden tegn til, ikke holdepunkt for, intet holdepunkt for	None, no, there is no, nothing, not, without, surgical, intraoperative, perioperative, intraoperative, risk of, risk of complications, possibility of, risks of, complications:, refuted, ruled out, disproved, denied, negated, no signs of, no sign of, no evidence of, without signs of, no basis for, no evidence to suggest, no basis whatsoever for	Words or phrases preceding (80 characters) a positive bleeding match indicate absence of bleeding, informed consent and risk-communication phrases.
Post-hit negation	Ingen/intet blodtab registreret, ingen blodtab, intet blodtab, ingen blødning, intet blødning, ingen tegn til blødning, uden tegn til blødning, ca. Xml / cirka X ml / omkring X ml / anslåetX ml / estimeret X ml / forventet Xml / samlet X ml / i alt X ml / <X ml / >X ml / ≤X ml / ≥X ml / X ml X: et vilkårligt tal	No blood loss recorded, no blood loss, no bleeding, no signs of bleeding, without signs of bleeding, approx. X ml / approximately X ml / around X ml / estimated X ml / estimated X ml / expected X ml / total X ml / in total X ml / <X ml / >X ml / ≤X ml / ≥X ml / X ml X: any given number	Phrases with explicit no-blood-loss or documented blood loss as a numeric volume (e.g. '100 ml') 80 characters following a positive bleeding match indicate no bleeding and is classified as negative. This is to capture documentation patterns in which a bleeding term appears as a heading or label, as well as notes in which intraoperative blood loss is recorded as a specific numeric volume, indicating routine surgical haemorrhage rather than a block-related complication.
Irrelevant bleeding context	CVK, centralvenekateter / central venekateter / central-vene-kateter, centralvenekateter / centralvene-kateter, centralt	Central venous catheter (all compound variants, compact compound and adjectival forms), CVC, neuraxial block (all inflected	Bleeding documented in the context of central venous catheterisation (CVC), epidural anaesthesia, spinal anaesthesia, lumbar puncture, dural

	<p>venekateter, neuroaksial / neuroaksiale / neuroaksialt, neuro aksial / neuro-aksial, neuraxial, neuroaksial blokade / neuroaksialblokade, neuroaksial blok / neuroaksialblok, neuro-aksial blokade / neuro aksial blokade, neuro-aksial blok / neuro aksial blok, neuraxial block / neuraxialblock, epidural / epidurale / epiduralt / epiduralen / epiduraler / epiduralkateter / epiduralanæstesi, EDA, epi, epiduralkateter / epidural kateter / epidural-kateter, spinal / spinale / spinalt / spinalen / spinalanæstesi / spinalpunktur / spinalkateter, spinalanæstesi / spinal anæstesi / spinal-anæstesi / spinal anesthesi, spinalpunktur / spinalpunkturen / spinalpunkturer, lumbalpunktur / lumbalpunkturen / lumbalpunkturer, durapunktur / durapunkturen / durapunkturer</p>	<p>forms, spaced / hyphenated variant, English/international spelling and short forms), epidural (all inflected forms and compounds), EDA (epidural anaesthesia - Danish abbreviation), epi (abbreviation for epidural), epidural catheter, spinal (all inflected forms and compounds), spinal anaesthesia, spinal puncture, lumbar puncture, dural puncture.</p>	<p>puncture, or neuraxial blockade. The filter is applied within a window of 100 characters on each side of a match of a bleeding term . If any of the these prespecified terms is found within that window, the match is excluded. .</p>
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Appendix 2 – Definition of the variables antithrombotic medication (Y/N) and relevant interruption before peripheral nerve block (PNB) procedure (Y/N).

Data sources		
Parameter	Value	Rationale
Prescription list	Dispensed prescriptions within 3 months before the PNB procedure.	A recently dispensed prescription is considered evidence of current antithrombotic treatment before the PNB procedure.
In-hospital Medication Administration Record (MDA)	Registration in the medication Administration Record (MDA) during admission, before the PNB procedure.	The MDA captures antithrombotic treatment prescribed, paused or administered during the admission, including treatment that may not be reflected by the patient's prescription lists.
Included antithrombotic drug classes		
ATC code	Drug class	Inclusion rule
B01AA	Vitamin K antagonists	Included.
B01AX05	Indirect factor Xa inhibitor (fondaparinux)	Included when the daily dosage exceeds 2.5 mg
B01AE, B01AF	Direct oral anticoagulants (DOAC) (rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, dabigatran)	Included
B01AB	Low molecular weight heparins (LMWH) (enoxaparin, tinzaparin, dalteparin)	Included, except B01AB10 (Tinzaparin), B01AB04 (Dalteparin) and B01AB05 (Enoxaparin) when the registered dose is ≤ 3500 IU, as this dosage does not warrant interruption(REF).
B01AC	P2Y12 inhibitors (clopidogrel, prasugrel, ticagrelor)	Included, except B01AC06 (acetylsalicylic acid/ASA) and B01AC11 (iloprost).

Antithrombotic therapy (Y/N)	
Search rule	Interpretation
The variable is coded Yes if either dispensed prescriptions or MDA contain eligible antithrombotic medication before the PNB procedure.	The combined approach captures both outpatient and inpatient antithrombotic therapy.

Relevant interruption before peripheral nerve block (PNB) procedure (Y/N)	
<p>Time intervals and dosage criteria are in accordance with the Peripheral Regional Anaesthesia and Bleeding Risk report by the Danish Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis[13], including time intervals, dosage specific time intervals and reduced kidney function.</p> <p>In general, registration in the MDA takes precedence as time-stamped administration data are considered more reliable than prescriptions and free-text documentation for determining when a drug was last administered.</p> <p>When INR og eGRF (estimated glomerular filtration rate) level is part of the assessment, the latest INR or eGFR measured within 7 days before PNB placement is used.</p>	
Yes	No
If ALL identified eligible antithrombotic agents are relevantly interrupted.	At least one identified agent fails the interruption criterion, was administered too close to PNB placement, or lacks documentation supporting relevant interruption where free-text confirmation is required.

Derivation of relevant interruption before PNB procedure		
Step	Data condition	Rationale
1. Identify eligible antithrombotic agents	All eligible antithrombotic drugs identified from dispensed prescriptions and/or MDA before the PNB procedure.	The interruption variable is based on all antithrombotic drugs identified before the PNB procedure.
2. Use MDA administration data when available	If the administration of an eligible antithrombotic drug is documented in the MDA before the PNB procedure, the time from the latest administration to the PNB procedure is calculated.	Actual administration timing is the most direct evidence for whether a sufficient interruption interval was achieved.
3. Use free-text search when information is not found in the MDA.	If 1) the drug is listed in MDA but is not administered or interruption not registered, and/or 2) if the patient has a prescription for an eligible antithrombotic drug without administration in MDA, the interruption is determined based on free-text search in clinical notes in the medical record 3 months before PNB procedure, for documentation of interruption, discontinuation, or absence of antithrombotic treatment.	Free-text documentation is used as supplementary evidence when structured administration data cannot determine whether the drug was paused.

Free-text search in clinical notes for documented interruption of antithrombotic treatment		
Parameter	Value	Rationale
Note retrieval time window	Clinical notes recorded up to 3 months before PNB placement.	The same look-back period as the prescription search is used to identify documented interruption or absence of antithrombotic treatment before the procedure.
Medication terms	Brand names, generic names, abbreviations and class-level terms for antithrombotic therapy.	The search is designed to capture both specific drugs and non-specific clinical wording such as "blood-thinning treatment" or "anticoagulation".
Pause-positive terms	Terms indicating interruption, discontinuation, stopping, or temporary pause.	These terms support that antithrombotic therapy was interrupted before the PNB procedure.
Pause-negative terms	Terms indicating no pause, not paused, not discontinued, or without interruption.	These terms indicate that treatment was not interrupted and therefore before the PNB procedure.

Classification logic	A note is flagged as indicating pre-procedural suspension if it matches pause-positive terms AND does not match pause-negative terms within the same note. Case-insensitive matching, meaning that both upper and lowercase letters are allowed, is applied throughout (ignore_case = TRUE).	Documentation of pause-negative term overrides the pause-positive terms since active clinical decision making of discontinuing an antithrombotic drug has been made, and indicates that at least one antithrombotic agent was continued. This minimises the risk of misclassification.
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Free-text search components

```

med_words <- paste(c("eliquis", "apixaban", "xarelto", "rivaroxaban", "lixiana", "edoxaban", "pradaxa", "dabigatran",
"marevan", "warfarin", "marcoumar", "phenprocoumon", "fragmin", "dalteparin", "innohep", "tinzaparin",
"enoxaparin", "inhixa", "fondaparinux", "arixtra", "clopidogrel", "plavix", "prasugrel", "efient", "ticagrelor", "brilique", "ak",
"ak[-\\s]*behandling", "noak", "doak", "blod\\s*fortyndende", "antikoagulation", "antikoagulerende", "antikoagulans",
"antikoagulations[-\\s]*behandling", "trombocythæmmende"), collapse = "|")
pause_positive_regex <- regex( paste0("\\bpaus\\w*\\s+(af|med|fra|for|i|pgal\\.?)grundet)?\\s*(, med_words,
")\\b"),
paste0("\\b(, med_words, ")\\b.{0,50}\\bpaus\\w*\\b"), "\\bhold\\w*\\s+pause\\b", "\\bmidlertid\\s+pause\\b",
past0("\\bseponer\\w*.{0,50}\\b(", med_words, ")\\b") paste0("\\b(", med_words, ")\\b.{0,50}\\bseponer\\w*\\b"),
paste0("\\b(ophør\\w*|stoppet|standset|sat\\s+il\\s+ber)\\b.{0,50}\\b(", med_words, ")\\b"), paste0("\\b(", med_words,
")\\b.{0,50}\\b(ophør\\w*|stoppet|standset|sat\\s+il\\s+bero)\\b"), "\\b(pt\\l\\.?)patient(?:en)?\\s+er\\s+ikke\\s+il\\s+blod\\s*fortynden
de\\s+behandling\\b", "\\bikke\\s+il\\s+blod\\s*fortyndende\\s+behandling\\b", "\\bingen\\s+blod\\s*fortyndende\\s+behandling\\b",
"\\bikke\\s+il\\s+behandling\\s+ed\\s+(trombocythæmmende|ak|ak[-
\\s]*behandling|antikoagulation|antikoagulans|blod\\s*fortyndende)\\b",
"\\bingen\\s+behandling\\s+med\\s+(trombocythæmmende|ak|ak[-
\\s]*behandling|antikoagulation|antikoagulans|blod\\s*fortyndende)\\b", "\\bikke\\s+il\\s+(ak|antikoagulations|[-
\\s]*behandling\\b", "\\bingen\\s+(ak|antikoagulations|[-\\s]*behandling\\b"), collapse = "|"), ignore_case = TRUE)
pause_negative_regex <- regex(paste0("\\buden\\s+pause\\b", "\\bikke\\s+paus\\w*\\b", "\\bej\\s+paus\\w*\\b",
"\\bingen\\s+paus\\w*\\b", "\\bikke\\s+seponer\\w*\\b", "\\bej\\s+seponer\\w*\\b", "\\bikke\\s+ophør\\w*\\b", "\\bej\\s+ohør\\w*\\b"),
collapse = "|") ignore_case = TRUE)

```

med_words
Regular-expression components covering named antithrombotic agents (brand and generic names) and generic class terms. All terms are matched case-insensitively, allowing spelling with both upper and lowercase letters.

Regex component	Matched words (Danish)	Explanation
"eliquis", "apixaban", "xarelto", "rivaroxaban", "lixiana", "edoxaban", "pradaxa", "dabigatran", "marevan", "warfarin", "marcoumar", "phenprocoumon", "fragmin", "dalteparin", "innohep", "tinzaparin", "enoxaparin", "inhixa", "fondaparinux", "arixtra", "clopidogrel", "plavix", "prasugrel", "efient", "ticagrelor", "brilique"	eliquis, apixaban, xarelto, rivaroxaban, lixiana, edoxaban, pradaxa, dabigatran, marevan, warfarin, marcoumar, phenprocoumon, fragmin, dalteparin, innohep, tinzaparin, enoxaparin, inhixa, fondaparinux, arixtra, clopidogrel, plavix, prasugrel, efient, ticagrelor, brilique	Brand names and generic names for all antithrombotics included in the study.
ak	ak	Common Danish clinical shorthand for antikoagulation (anticoagulation). Word boundary enforced to prevent spurious matches (e.g. akut).
ak[-\\s]*behandling	ak-behandling / ak behandling	Expanded form: "antikoagulationsbehandling" (anticoagulation treatment). Hyphen or space permitted.
noak	noak	Danish acronym for non-vitamin K oral anticoagulants (NOAC/DOAC). Covers apixaban, rivaroxaban, edoxaban, dabigatran.

doak	doak	Alternative Danish acronym: "direkte oral antikoagulantia" (direct oral anticoagulants). Used interchangeably with noak.
blod\s*fortyndende	blodfortyndende / blod fortyndende	Lay and clinical term: blood-thinning / anticoagulant or antiplatelet therapy. Space between components is optional.
antikoagulation	antikoagulation	Standard clinical term: anticoagulation.
antikoagulerende	antikoagulerende	Adjectival form: anticoagulant treatment.
antikoagulans	antikoagulans	Noun form: anticoagulant agent.
antikoagulations[-s]*behandling	antikoagulationsbehandling / antikoagulations-behandling / antikoagulations behandling	Full compound noun: anticoagulation treatment. Hyphen or space permitted.
trombocythæmmende	trombocythæmmende	Antiplatelet (literally: platelet-inhibiting). Covers aspirin, clopidogrel, prasugrel, and ticagrelor.
<p>pause_positive_regex — patterns indicating pre-procedural suspension Regular-expression components identifying free-text documentation that a patient's antithrombotic therapy was suspended, discontinued, or absent at the time of the peripheral nerve block procedure. Where (<med_words>) appears in the regex column, it represents the full alternation of all med_words.</p>		
Regex component	Matched words (Danish)	Explanation
\bpausw*\s+(af med fra for i pga\.\? grundet)?\s*(<med_words>)\b	pauseret X / pause af X / pausering for X / pauseret pga. X / pauseret grundet X X: any med_words	All inflected forms of 'pausere' (pause/suspension) followed by an optional preposition (of, with, on, because of, due to) and any term from med_words.
\b(<med_words>)\b.{0,50}\bpausw*\b	X ... pauseret / X ... pausering / X ... pause X: any med_words	Reverse-order variant: medication term precedes a form of pause or suspension 'pausere' captured within 50 characters.
\bholdw*\s+pause\b	holdt pause / holder pause	Phrase meaning 'is taking a break from' treatment. All inflected forms of 'holde' (taking) followed by 'pause' (suspension/interruption)
\bmidlertidw*\s+pause\b	midlertidigt pause / midlertidig pause	Phrase meaning 'temporary suspension'. Covers both adjectival forms (temporary /temporarily).
\bseponerw*.{0,50}(<med_words>)\b	seponeret X / seponeres X / seponering af X X: any med_words	All inflected forms of 'seponere' (suspension) followed within 50 characters by any medication term. Implies full discontinuation rather than temporary suspension.
\b(<med_words>)\b.{0,50}\bseponerw*\b	X ... seponeret / X ... seponeres X: any med_words	Reverse-order variant: medication term precedes the discontinuation verb within 50 characters.
\b(ophørw* stoppet standset sat\s+i\s+bero)\b.{0,50}\b(<med_words>)\b	ophørt med X / stoppet X / standset X / sat i bero pga. X X: any med_words	Cessation verbs followed within 50 characters by a medication term. 'Ophøre' = to cease; 'stoppe' = to stop; 'standse' = to halt; 'sætte i bero' = to put on hold.

<code>\b(<med_words>)\b.{0,50}\b(ophør\w* standset sat\s+i\s+bero)\b</code>	X ... ophørt / X ... stoppet / X ... standset X: any med_words	Reverse-order variant: medication term precedes the cessation verb within 50 characters.
<code>\bptl.?\s+er\s+ikke\s+i\s+blod\s*fortyndende\s+behandling\b</code>	pt. er ikke i blodfortyndende behandling / pt er ikke i blod fortyndende behandling / patienten er ikke i blod fortyndende behandling	Standard clinical phrase: 'the patient is not on antithrombotic treatment'. Covers abbreviated (pt.) and unabbreviated (pt) forms.
<code>\bikke\s+i\s+blod\s*fortyndende\s+behandling\b</code>	ikke i blodfortyndende behandling / ikke i blod fortyndende behandling	Shorter variant of the above, without the subject prefix.
<code>\bingen\s+blod\s*fortyndende\s+behandling\b</code>	ingen blodfortyndende behandling / ingen blod fortyndende behandling	Alternative phrasing: 'no antithrombotic treatment'.
<code>\bikke\s+i\s+behandling\s+med\s+(trombocythæmmende ak ak[-\s]*behandling antikoagulation antikoagulans blod\s*fortyndende)\b</code>	ikke i behandling med trombocythæmmende / ikke i behandling med AK / ikke i behandling med antikoagulation	Phrase: not on treatment with antiplatelet treatment (=trombocythæmmende). Covers the key generic class terms used in clinical records.
<code>\bingen\s+behandling\s+med\s+(trombocythæmmende ak ak[-\s]*behandling antikoagulation antikoagulans blod\s*fortyndende)\b</code>	ingen behandling med trombocythæmmende / ingen behandling med AK-behandling / ingen behandling med antikoagulans	Alternative phrasing: with antiplatelet treatment'.
<code>\bikke\s+i\s+(ak antikoagulations)[- \s]*behandling\b</code>	ikke i AK-behandling / ikke i ak behandling / ikke i antikoagulationsbehandling	Compact phrase: 'not on anticoagulation treatment'. Covers both AK shorthand and the full compound, with optional hyphen or space.
<code>\bingen\s+(ak antikoagulations)[- \s]*behandling\b</code>	ingen AK-behandling / ingen antikoagulationsbehandling	Alternative phrasing: 'no anticoagulation treatment'.
pause_negative_regex — patterns overriding a positive suspension match		
Regular-expression components that, when matched in the same note as a pause_positive_regex hit, override the positive classification. These patterns capture documentation explicitly stating that antithrombotic therapy was not suspended — indicating continuation of treatment through the perioperative period		
Regex component	Matched words (Danish)	Explanation
<code>\buden\s+pause\b</code>	uden pause	Phrase: 'without pause / without suspension'. Indicates antithrombotic therapy was continued without interruption.
<code>\bikke\s+paus\w*\b</code>	ikke pauseret / ikke pauseres / ikke pausering	Negation of all inflected forms of 'pausere': 'not suspended / not paused'.
<code>\bej\s+paus\w*\b</code>	ej pauseret / ej pauseres	Formal/archaic negation variant ('ej' = not).
<code>\\bingen\\s+paus\\w*\b</code>	ingen pause	Phrase: 'no pause / no suspension'. Indicates uninterrupted continuation of antithrombotic therapy.
<code>\bikke\s+seponer\w*\b</code>	ikke seponeret / ikke seponeres / ikke seponering	Negation of all inflected forms of 'seponere': 'not discontinued'.
<code>\bej\s+seponer\w*\b</code>	ej seponeret / ej seponeres	Formal/archaic negation variant.
<code>\bikke\s+ophør\w*\b</code>	ikke ophørt / ikke ophører / ikke ophørende	Negation of all inflected forms of 'ophøre': 'not ceased / not discontinued'.
<code>\bej\s+ophør\w*\b</code>	ej ophørt / ej ophører	Formal/archaic negation variant.

Appendix 3 - Variables overview

Primary outcome			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Clinically relevant post peripheral nerve block bleeding	Dichotomous (Y/N)	<p>Clinically significant bleeding post peripheral nerve block procedure identified by full patient journal audit after of one of following event:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Free text mining in the patient journal for any bleeding term occurring within 50 words from any block term, two hours before until seven days after the PNB procedure. All notes are then screened for relevant context of PNB procedure. See Appendix 1 for a full description of free text mining. 2) Vascular surgical or radiologic intervention required in the shoulder/neck region: exploration of the subclavian artery or the the common carotid artery (KPAA30, KPAA20), ligation of the subclavian artery or the common carotid artery (KPAB30, KPAB20), suture/repair of the subclavian artery (KPAC30), open arterial reconstruction/plasty of the subclavian artery or the common carotid artery (KPAN30, KPAN20), percutaneous angioplasty of the subclavian artery or the common carotid artery (KPAP30, KPAP20), exploration of arteria axillaris, brachialis, radialis, ulnaris or any other arteria on the upper extremity (KPBA, KPBA10, KPBA20, KPBA30, KPBA99), ligation of arteria axillaris, brachialis, radialis, ulnaris or any other arteria on the upper extremity (KPBB10, KPBB20, KPBB30, KPBB99), suture/repair of arteria axillaris, brachialis, radialis, ulnaris or any other arteria on the upper extremity (KPBC, KPBC10, KPBC20, KPBC30, KPBC99), open arterial reconstruction/plasty of arteria axillaris, brachialis, radialis, ulnaris or any other arteria on the upper extremity (KPBN, KPBN10, KPBN20, KPBN99), percutaneous angioplasty of the arteria axillaris, brachialis or any other artery on the upper extremity (KPBP10, KPBP20, KPBP99), other operations on arteries in the upper extremity (KPBW, KPBW99) 3) Haemothorax (DJ942 and DJ942A) and/or pleural drain (KGAA10c) 	From procedure until 7 days post procedure or until discharge, including readmission

		<p>4) CT angiography or ultrasound of vessels in the upper extremity: angiography of the neck vessels (BLD3092); angiography of the entire upper limb, bilateral/right/left (BLD3101, BLD3102, BLD3103); ultrasonography of the cervical vessels (ECH75); bedside ultrasonography performed by the treating clinician (PRO167); radiological Doppler ultrasonography of the upper-limb arteries (BLD3129, BLD3130, BLD3131), cervical arteries (BLD886), cervical veins (BLD889), and upper-limb veins (BLD3132, BLD3133, BLD3134).</p> <p>5) Blood aspiration during PNB procedure</p>	
Secondary outcomes			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Post peripheral nerve block length of stay	Continuous (hours)	Time from peripheral nerve block procedure until discharge	From procedure until discharge
Readmission within 30 days post peripheral nerve block	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Readmission to hospital within 30 days post peripheral nerve block procedure	From procedure until 30 days after discharge
Exposure variables			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Antithrombotic therapy	Dichotomous (Y/N)	<p>Antithrombotic therapy in prescription or administered during admission prior to peripheral nerve block procedure defined as use of ≥ 1 of the following agents without relevant temporary pre-procedural suspension according to guidelines in the Peripheral Regional Anaesthesia and Bleeding Risk report by the Danish Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis, table 6.2.2 [13]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vitamin K antagonists (VKA) (warfarin, phenprocoumon) • Low molecular weight heparins > 3.500 IE (LMWH) (dalteparin, enoxaparin, tinzaparin) • Direct oral anticoagulants (DOAC) (rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, dabigatran) • Fondaparinux • P2Y12 inhibitors (clopidogrel, prasugrel, ticagrelor) 	At procedure

Biochemical coagulopathy	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Coagulopathy at the time of the peripheral nerve block procedure defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following biochemical criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Normalized Ratio (INR) ≥ 1.5[13] Thrombocytes in plasma $< 20 \times 10^9/L$ [13] 	Latest biochemical value within 90 days prior to procedure
Peripheral nerve block type	Categorical	Documented peripheral nerve block procedure in the procedural documentation: Deep block: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infraclavicular Superficial block: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Axillary Interscalene Supraclavicular Suprascapular Single nerve blocks (radial, ulnar, median or musculocutaneous or a combination hereof) 	At procedure
Covariates			
Injection technique	Dichotomous (single shot or continuous catheter)	Documented injection technique for the peripheral nerve block procedure in the procedural documentation (single-shot or continuous catheter)	At procedure
Type of surgical procedure performed	Categorical	SKS-code of the surgery performed which the PNB procedure is linked to in the database.	At procedure
Time between PNB procedure and surgery (hours)	Continuous (+/-hours)	Amount of hours between the PNB procedure and beginning of surgery with PNBs performed before surgery being negative amount and PNBs performed after being positive.	From PNB procedure until beginning of surgery.
Intraoperative blood loss (mL)	Continuous (mL)	Documented blood loss in mL during the surgery for which the peripheral nerve block procedure was performed	From beginning of surgery until end of surgery
Baseline variables and study characteristics			
Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Sex	Dichotomous (male or female)	Male or female	At admission
Age	Categorical	18-29, 30-44, 45-59, 60-74 or >75 years	At admission
BMI	Categorical	<18.5 , 18.5-24.9, 25-29.9 or ≥ 30 kg/m ²	At admission

American Society of Anesthesiology classification (ASA)	Categorical	ASA I: Healthy patient, ASA II: Mild systemic disease, ASA III: Severe systemic disease, ASA IV: Severe systemic disease with constant threat to life	At admission
Admission type	Dichotomous (acute or elective surgery)	Acute or elective classification of the booking of the surgery for which the peripheral nerve block was performed	At admission
Hospital site	Categorical	Hospital location categorized in The Capital Region (site A-F) and Zealand Region (site G-I) of Denmark.	At admission
Indication for PNB procedure	Dichotomous (primary anaesthesia or postoperative pain relief)	Documented indication for the peripheral nerve block in the procedural documentation (primary anaesthesia or postoperative pain relief)	At procedure
90-day all-cause mortality	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Death registered within 90 days post peripheral nerve block procedure regardless of the cause	From procedure until 90 days post procedure
Blood aspiration during procedure	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Documented blood aspiration during the peripheral nerve block procedure in the procedural documentation	At procedure
Latest pre-procedure creatinine	Continuous ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	Latest creatinine value within 90 days prior to the peripheral nerve block procedure	Pre-procedure
Latest pre-procedure haemoglobin	Continuous (mmol/l)	Latest haemoglobin value within 90 days prior to the peripheral nerve block procedure	Pre-procedure
Latest pre-procedure thrombocytes	Continuous (mia/L)	Latest thrombocytes value within 90 days prior to the peripheral nerve block procedure	Pre-procedure
Latest pre-procedure INR	Continuous	Latest International Normalized Ratio (INR) value within 90 days prior to the peripheral nerve block procedure	Pre-procedure
Comorbidity - liver disease	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following diagnoses identified by ICD-10 codes: Alcoholic liver disease (K70), toxic liver disease (K71), hepatic insufficiency (K72), chronic hepatitis (K73), liver fibrosis and cirrhosis (K74), other types of liver inflammation (K75), other liver diseases (K76) or varicer i spiserøret (I85)	At admission
Comorbidity - kidney disease	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following diagnoses identified by ICD-10 codes: Acute kidney disease (N17) or chronic kidney disease (N18)	At admission
Comorbidity - Diabetes	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following diagnoses identified by ICD-10 codes: Diabetes mellitus (E10, E11, E12, E13, E14)	At admission

Comorbidity – ischaemic heart disease	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following diagnoses identified by ICD-10 codes: Ischaemic heart disease (I21, I22, I23, I24, I25)	At admission
Comorbidity – Atrial fibrillation or atrial flutter	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following identified by ICD-10 codes: Atrial fibrillation or atrial flutter (I480, I481, I482, I483, I484, I489)	At admission
Comorbidity – arterial sclerosis	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following at admission identified by ICD-10 codes: Arterial sclerosis (I70, I700, I701, I702, I708, I709)	At admission
Comorbidity- Coagulopathy diagnosis	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Coagulopathy diagnosis at the time of the peripheral nerve block procedure defined as the presence of ≥ 1 of the following diagnoses identified by ICD-10 codes at admission: Haemophilia A (DD669), haemophilia B (DD679), haemophilia without further specification (DD669A), single-factor deficiencies (I, II, V, VII, VIII (DD66), IX (DD67), X, XI (DD681), XIII), other coagulopathies (DD68), acquired coagulation factor deficiency (DD684), coagulopathy without further specification (DD689), acquired coagulation factor deficiency due to hypoprothrombinemia (DD684A), inherited deficiency of other coagulation factors (DD682), acquired coagulation factor deficiency due to vitamin K deficiency (DD684B), acquired coagulation factor deficiency due to liver disease (DD684C), disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) (DD65), purpura and other haemorrhagic conditions (DD69) or Von Willebrands disease (DD680)	At admission
All-cause mortality within 7 days	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Death registered within 7 days post-PNB procedure regardless of the cause of death	From the end of PNB procedure until 7 days after PNB procedure
Transfusion of red blood cells units	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Transfusion of red blood cells units registered within 48 hours after PNB procedure [23]	From PNB procedure registration until 48 hours after
Decrease of hemoglobin > 1.24 mmol/L (>2 g/dL) within seven days after PNB procedure	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Decrease of hemoglobin > 1.24 mmol/L (>2 g/dL) [23] measured by the difference between latest pre-PNB-procedure hemoglobin within 30 days, if unavailable the average hemoglobin over the past 90 days is used compared to the lowest measured hemoglobin within seven days post-PNB procedure.	From PNB procedure registration until seven days after